

Electrophoretic Mobility of Oil-Droplets Dispersed in Aqueous Solution of Fulvic Acid

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The electrophoretic mobility of oil-droplets dispersed in the aqueous solution of fulvic acids has been measured at ionic strengths 0.01 and 0.10. The oils used are benzene, toluene and xylene. From the values of U , ζ -potentials have been evaluated. It has been observed that ζ increases with the increase in adsorption. It is evident that within the range of concentration of FA_n for which the plot of ζ vs. $\log C$ is linear, the ratio of Stern layer potential to ζ -potential remains constant.

OIL droplets dispersed in an aqueous solution of long chain ions carry an electric charge on their surface and move when an electric field is applied. The measurement of zeta-potential of the oil droplets stabilised by a number of cationic and anionic detergents has been carried out by several investigators^{1,2}. The effect of adding Al, Fe, Ca, Mg and Cu-ions to a humic compound on its electrophoretic mobility has been observed by Juste *et al*³.

In earlier works^{4,5,6,7} of the author it has been established that humic, hymatomelanic and fulvic acids extracted from soil and prepared synthetically can be used to stabilise the oil droplets dispersed in water. The role of these acids as stabiliser has been studied by using two methods, namely,

(i) Direct estimation of acid before and after dispersion of a given volume of oil in a given volume of aqueous solution of acid,

(ii) Measurement of lowering of interfacial tension (γ) combined with Gibbs equation.

Recently, the work on adsorption of humic and hymatomelanic acids at air/water and oil/water interfaces has been reported by other workers^{8,9}. Chen and Schnitzer¹⁰ have measured the surface tension of aqueous solutions of soil humic substances.

In the present investigation, the electrophoretic mobility of oil droplets dispersed in the aqueous solution of FA_n has been measured by the micro-cathaphoretic method¹¹. The adsorbed amount of FA_n per unit area of the interface has been evaluated using Gibbs isotherm in the form,

$$\Gamma = - \frac{1}{RT} \frac{d\gamma}{d \ln C}$$

since in these experiments a sufficient excess of added neutral electrolyte is

always present to keep the ionic strength constant. The dependence of zeta-potential on the amount of stabiliser ions adsorbed per unit area and hence on the concentration of the stabiliser in the aqueous phase has been discussed in the light of experimental data.

Experimental

Fulvic acid (FA) isolated from Palampur soil has been selected. The isolation procedure is the same as adopted earlier¹². It has not been possible to use synthetic fulvic acid (FA_s) and two other components of humus, namely, humic and hymatomelanic acids as stabilisers because of their dark colour which impeded clear vision of the dispersed oil droplets.

Purity of the constituents : The purity of natural fulvic acid (FA_n) has been discussed previously¹². NaCl used has been found free from surfactant contamination by surface tension measurement. Oils used are benzene, toluene and xylene, all being products of E. Merck. They have been redistilled. It is not known whether xylene used is a single isomer or a mixture of all the three; the fraction boiling at 138.5° has been collected and used in the present investigation.

Preparation of emulsions : The emulsions used have been prepared by shaking and homogenizing 10ml of oil with 100ml of water. They have been suitably diluted to a given volume with the aqueous solution of FA_n . The measurements have been carried out at two ionic strengths, 0.01 and 0.10, maintained by adding pure NaCl. All the emulsions have been prepared keeping the ratio of oil to water constant, varying only the concentration of FA_n in the aqueous phase.

Measurement of electrophoretic mobility : The

procedure adopted is the same as that described by Chakraborty and Ghosh¹¹. The microcataphoretic cell with its plane vertical and the axis of the microscope horizontal used by Chattoraj and Bull² has been adopted for the measurements with some further modifications. Komagata¹³ determined the position of the stationary layer in the flat cell and on the basis of his result, the velocity of the droplets in the stationary layer at 0.2d has been measured, where d represents depth of the cell. The ratio of the width : depth in the cell used is 10 : 1.

The observed electrophoretic mobility, *u*, of the droplet which traverses a distance, *d* cm, in *t* seconds under the potential gradient, *F*, is given by the relation :

$$u = \frac{d}{t.F} = \frac{d}{t \left(\frac{i}{S.A} \right)} = \frac{d.S.A}{i.t} = \frac{d.k.A}{i.R.t}$$

where, *A*=area of the cross-section of the microcataphoretic cell=0.2517 sq. cm. in the apparatus used,

S=specific bulk conductance of the solution, =*k*/*R*, where *k* is the cell constant of the conductance cell and *R* the observed resistance and

i=current in ampere.

Evaluation of ζ : For each concentration of the stabiliser, *FA_n*, the values of mobility, *u*, of a fairly large number of globules have been calculated and their average has been taken. From these data the values of ζ -potential have been calculated using the equation :

$$\zeta = \frac{4\pi\eta}{D} \times u \times (300)^2 V$$

$$\left(a \gg \frac{1}{\chi} \right)$$

where,

D=dielectric constant of the dispersion medium,

η =viscosity of the same dispersion medium,

a=average diameter of the particle, and

$\frac{1}{\chi}$ = the Debye-Hückel distance.

Discussion

The data (not given) show that the rate of increase of electrophoretic mobility with the increase in concentration of *FA_n* for emulsions having ionic strengths 0.01 and 0.10 is quite small.

In Figures 1 and 2, the values of *u* at ionic strengths 0.01 and 0.10 respectively have been

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

plotted against *I'*, i.e., the amount in gm. of *FA_n* per cm². A linear relationship between *u* and *I'* has been noticed within the range of concentration investigated. A steady increase of the electrophoretic mobilities as well as of the zeta-potentials with the increase in concentration of *FA_n* is observed for all the systems investigated (not shown). It is also to be noticed that the values of electrophoretic mobility and hence ζ -potential is appreciably lower at 0.1 than at 0.01.

The values of ζ -potential have been plotted against log *C* at ionic strengths 0.01 (Fig. 3) and 0.10 (Fig. 4). It may be noticed that ζ -log *C* plot yields a straight line over a certain range of concentration of *FA_n* investigated. The ranges of

concentration for which this linearity between ζ and $\log C$ holds good are recorded in Table-1.

According to Verwey and Overbeek's theory¹⁴

where C_t = total concentration of the electrolytes

$$\text{or } \psi_o = \frac{2kT}{e} \ln \frac{\text{const}}{\sqrt{C_t}} + \frac{2kT}{e} \ln n \quad \dots (1)$$

TABLE-1 RANGE OF CONC. IN GM/ML FOR WHICH ζ -LOG C RELATION IS LINEAR

Interface	Ionic Strength = 0.01	Ionic Strength = .10
Benzene/Water	0.510×10^{-3} to 3.060×10^{-3}	0.510×10^{-3} to 3.060×10^{-3}
Toluene/Water	0.510×10^{-3} to 2.550×10^{-3}	0.510×10^{-3} to 2.805×10^{-3}
Xylene/Water	1.020×10^{-3} to 3.060×10^{-3}	1.020×10^{-3} to 3.060×10^{-3}

when the electrochemical potential, $\psi_o > 100$ mV and the charge density, $\rho = en$ where n is the number

Here, all the terms have their usual significance.

It is evident from our earlier observations^{4,5} that Freundlich isotherm¹⁸ holds good for the adsorption of FA_n in presence of neutral electrolyte at oil/water interface over the range of concentration of FA_n investigated. The actual isotherm of Freundlich type which holds good in presence of salt is

$$n = K \cdot C_t^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

$$\text{or } \ln n = \frac{1}{3} \ln C + \ln K$$

Putting this value of $\ln n$ in equation (1), we have,

$$\psi_o = \frac{2kT}{e} \ln \frac{\text{const}}{\sqrt{C_t}} + \frac{2kT}{e} \ln K + \frac{2kT}{3e} \ln C$$

$$\text{or } \psi_o = \text{const} + \frac{2RT}{3F} \ln C \quad \dots (2)$$

Since the first term in the R.H.S of equation (1) is constant for a definite ionic strength we may write the equation (2) as

$$\frac{\psi_o - \zeta}{\zeta} + \frac{\zeta}{\zeta} = \frac{\text{const.}}{\zeta} + \frac{2RT}{3F\zeta} \ln C \quad \dots (3)$$

Putting $\frac{\psi_o - \zeta}{\zeta} = P$ where $\psi_o - \zeta$ = potential of the Stern layer,

ζ = potential of the diffuse double layer, the equation (3) can be written in the following form

$$(P+1) = \frac{\text{const.}}{\zeta} + \frac{2RT}{3F\zeta} \ln C$$

$$\zeta = \frac{\text{const.}}{(P+1)} + \frac{2RT}{3(P+1)F} \ln C$$

$$= \text{const.} + \frac{2RT}{3(P+1)F} \ln C$$

Since the relation between ζ and $\ln C$ is linear, it may be concluded that within the range of concentration of FA_n for which this linearity holds good, P , the ratio of the Stern layer potential to ζ -potential remains constant.

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

of long-chain ions adsorbed per unit area of the interface and is equal to $\Gamma \times N$, where N is the Avogadro number, then $\rho = \text{constant} \sqrt{C_t}$. exp.

$$\frac{e\psi_o}{2kT} = en$$

$$\text{or } \exp \frac{e\psi_o}{2kT} = \frac{en}{\text{const.} \sqrt{C_t}}$$

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